

R = T(D + C) + M ... and what else?

By Noel Chia Kok Hwee

Reading is uniquely human and most complex of all cognitive activities. For reading to become successful, it requires many basic processes of decoding (e.g., letter identification, letter-sound association, word recognition, and syntax) to work sequentially and simultaneously. Reading also requires additional, higher-order thinking processes (e.g., inference making, reasoning, and self-monitoring) for the purpose of establishing meaningful comprehension. In short, I might sum the reading process in one lateral equation: $R = T(D + C) + M$, where R is reading, T is thinking, D is decoding, C is Comprehension, and M is Motivation. Both D and C need T in order to function coherently and cohesively. Of course, there is more to the whole equation. Word knowledge, topic knowledge, socio-cultural context, and general intelligence are just as essential to be incorporated into the equation. However, I shall not dwell on them, lest the equation becomes too complicated and the whole article becomes too academic. I do not want to end up talking about the calculus of reading.

Back to our equation of reading: $R = T(D + C) + M$. Without T, D will be mere barking at print; without T, C is meaningless and a reader becomes hyperlexic, that is, reading without real understanding. M is also a very important addend in this equation. A successful reader is a motivated person who loves to read and wants to read. The ultimate aim, as I see it, is for every reader to learn from a given text, that is, to recognize the depicted facts or events, to connect them to each other and to his/her background knowledge and experience, and to

memorize the results so that they can be used later. Hence, one important aim of reading education is to provide our children with the tools to perform these requisite basic decoding and higher-order thinking processes.

In the past decade, tremendous advances have been made in understanding how readers with different ability levels comprehend, store, and retrieve text information. The purpose of this article is to provide an overview of reader profiles and to explore their implications for teaching or facilitation of reading education. The first section outlines the four main reader profiles, and the second section explores the process of reading facilitation according to the different needs of respective reader profiles.

The Reader Profiles

The ability to decode (D) and comprehend (C) what is read, while pondering or thinking (T) about the writer's intent, and the motivation (M) to do so form the key to successful reading (R) and hence, successful learning of academic subjects in school and also acquiring new skills and knowledge. The job of a teacher would have been made easier if every child possessed that ability and motivation. However, not everyone is going to make it as such. There are those who are avid readers and they need not be pushed to read. There are also others who must be reminded or coerced to read. There are still others who dislike reading because they are having some form of reading disability. Then there are those who do not read because they cannot read, or are illiterate.

Focus Two

Figure 1: Model of 4 Reader Types

<p>Independent Reader Can read and does read $R = T\uparrow(D\uparrow + C\uparrow) + M\uparrow$</p>	<p>Reluctant Reader Can read and does not read $R = T(D + C) + M\downarrow$</p>
<p>Illiterate Does not read because cannot read $R = T(D + C) + M$</p>	<p>Disabled Reader Can read but with difficulty $R = T(D\downarrow + C) + M$ $R = T(D + C\downarrow) + M$ $R = T(D\downarrow + C\downarrow) + M$</p>

At this juncture, I want to present a theoretical model to profile four main reader types (see Figure 1) – the independent, the reluctant, the disabled, and the illiterate – and discuss briefly each of the reader type. However, I want to stress that readers should not be defined by any one of the four profiles. The behavior, feelings and needs of each reader change frequently as he/she grows. The model (see Chia, 1994, 1998, 1999) I have proposed here is to provide a new understanding of the readers and opportunities for developing techniques utilized to improve reading skills or help to cope with academic demands, but not necessarily to improve the reading skills, and strategies for facilitating the reading

development of these readers. It is important for teachers, librarians, parents as well as other interested parties, such as reading facilitators, to know, understand and be able to identify the behaviors, feelings and needs of different readers so that they can do their part to promote reading habits amongst the children, whichever reader profiles they belong to.

Type 1 Reader: The Independent

Reading behavior: Can read and does read

Reading equation:

$R = T(D + C) + M$ where all the elements are positive and high-functioning

An independent reader is one who possesses some awareness and control of the cognitive activities he/she engages in as he/she reads. Most characteristics of independent readers include the following meta-cognitive skills and activities (Baker & Brown, 1982):

- Clarifying the purpose of reading (i.e., explicit and implicit comprehension);
- Identifying the important aspects of a message;
- Focusing attention on the major content rather than trivia;
- Monitoring on-going activities to determine if comprehension is taking place;
- Engaging in self-questioning to determine if goals are being achieved; and
- Taking corrective action when failures in comprehension are detected.

An independent reader moves from being a good reader to becoming an effective reader before achieving as a matured reader, monitoring what he/she reads and constantly does so automatically and unconsciously. This is to say the reader is no longer aware of monitoring (Adams, 1980).

Type 2 Reader: The Reluctant

Reading behavior: Can read but does not read

Reading equation:

$R = T(D + C) + M\downarrow$ where $M\downarrow$ is negative or low-functioning

A child who lacks confidence in the ability to read or to learn to read well is often referred to as a reluctant reader (also known as a slow or poor reader). Such a child may have very low motivation to read and this could be due to lack of interesting reading materials. Often such a child chooses to avoid reading

situations which he/she views as threat-producing, which results in his/her failure to practice the skills that he/she has already acquired, and through disuse, the child may actually lose some of the reading skills he/she once had. Reluctant readers have been described as unreflective and inconstant, forgetting what he/she is going, letting himself/herself be carried away by fantasy and caprice, and lacking directions (Binet, 1909).

Type 3 Reader: The Disabled

Reading behavior: Can read but with difficulty

Reading equation:

$R = T(D\downarrow + C) + M$ where $D\downarrow$ is negative or low functioning (dyslexic)

$R = T(D + C\downarrow) + M$ where $C\downarrow$ is negative or low functioning (hyperlexic)

$R = T(D\downarrow + C\downarrow) + M$ where both $D\downarrow$ and $C\downarrow$ are negative or low functioning (non-specific reading disorder)

The term, *the disabled*, has been deliberately chosen to reflect the fact that it is not about any one type of reading disability of any one origin or cause. It can be divided into two main categories: specific reading retardation and general reading backward. The former consists of three sub-categories (i.e., the dyslexic, the non-specific reading disabled, and the hyperlexic) and the latter includes those who are reading disabled because of mental retardation.

Broadly speaking, a disabled reader is one whose condition is that of being unable to thrive pedagogically, unable to profit from standard methods of instruction, and unable to learn to read (Money, 1966). The resultant defective literacy is to be distinguished from that which results simply from educational neglect or inadequate instruction. Characteristically speaking, the disabled reader is stuck at the beginner or near-beginner level, making the typical beginner's mistakes.

Type 4 Reader: The Illiterate

Reading behavior: Does not read because cannot read (unable to read)

Reading equation:

$R = T(\underline{D} + \underline{C}) + M$ where \underline{D} and \underline{C} are yet to be attained for basic literacy

To define the illiterate (also known as non-reader), there is a need to understand the term illiteracy. The term is far from being merely a technical problem and it is not just the absence of literacy. It is also a psychological and social force that deepens deprivation and poverty (Bolindo, 1983). An illiterate is unable to read and write and his/her illiteracy is linked to contextual factors which, in social class, gender, linguistic affiliation, general levels of socio-economic development, and exploitation, play important and mutually supportive functions (Stromquist, 1990).

In this last reader type, there are two categories: the reading illiterate and the functional illiterate. A reading illiterate is someone who is unable to understand and use those written language forms required by society and/or valued by an individual. Therefore, reading illiteracy involves more than the inability to recognize words. It also involves understanding, thinking and using words for the purposes of communication, information and knowledge.

Focus Two

Figure 2: Model of Reading Facilitation

A functional illiterate is one who cannot read or write sufficiently well to function effectively in all those activities in which literacy is normally assumed in his/her culture or group. That does not mean he/she cannot sign his/her name or read street signs, but that is about all he/she can do.

Reading Facilitation

Now that we know the four reader types, what can we as parents, teachers and/or librarians do to promote reading habits among our children? How can we facilitate reading among the children?

At a recent SRL Reading Facilitators' course conducted in July this year, I stressed the importance of proper facilitation of a reading program and briefly defined reading facilitation here as a process of making reading and learning to read easier so as to promote positive reading behavior or habits. Reading facilitation covers three essential roles: reader counseling, reader

coaching, and reader empowerment (see Figure 2) and they go hand-in-hand with the three reader types, i.e., the reluctant reader, the disabled reader and the independent reader respectively. The illiterate or non-reader has been excluded here because strictly speaking, a non-reader is not a reader, unless he/she has attained at least basic literacy. The three reading facilitation roles play an important part inculcating our children as readers. Let us briefly examine each of the three roles here.

Reading Facilitation Role 1: Reader Counseling

Reader Type: Reluctant Reader

Reading behavior: Can read but does not read

Reading equation:

$R = T(D + C) + M\downarrow$ where $M\downarrow$ is negative or low-functioning

The normal dictionary definition of *counseling* means to provide advice and support to someone with problems. When the word *reader* is added to it, our focus is now on a special client: the reader. However, there is more to it. I have coined the term *reader counseling* to refer to more than just providing mere advice and support to readers with problems. It includes the following tasks as briefly described below:

- To clarify what is important to the reader during his/her reading development;
- To get in touch with the reader's inner resources (i.e., background knowledge and prior experiences);
- In the exploration of feelings, thoughts and meanings particular to the reader;
- By offering support at times of problems encountered in reading and/or comprehension;
- By offering reading support during developmental and transitional periods from pre-literacy or emergent literacy phase to early literacy phase for instance;
- To work through "stuck" issues – this may involve integrating background knowledge and prior experiences; and

- To reach a resolution of reading and/or comprehension problems, which also include low motivation to read and poor self-esteem as a reader.

The meaning and role of reader counseling is constantly changing to meet the challenges of societal pressures and demands, which we often attempt to deal with at cost to our inner affective world. Our role as reader counselors, in particular, has been defined by the tasks described above and also in terms of its aims, which include providing a conducive environment (e.g., classroom and library) that enables the readers to work towards living in a more resourceful and personally fulfilling way (Milne,1999).

Reading Facilitation Role 2: Reader Coaching

Reader Type: Disabled Reader

Reading behavior: Can read but with difficulty

Reading equation:

R = T(D↓ + C) + M where D↓ is negative or low functioning (dyslexic)

R = T(D + C↓) + M where C↓ is negative or low functioning (hyperlexic)

R = T(D↓ + C↓) + M where both D↓ and C↓ are negative or low functioning

(non-specific reading disorder)

By the term reader coaching I refer to the concept of coaching, which is a remedial technique with roots in the work of Marie Clay. Clay (2001) viewed readers as active learners working to construct a self-extending system – a system that “bring(s) about new forms of mediation,” “alter(s) an existing working system to become more effective,” and “compile(s) more effective assemblies of systems” (p.136). One way our children can develop this system is through “powerful interactions with their teachers” during reading (p.136). Teachers closely observe them and intervene to support their developing strategic processes. Clay described this approach as an interactive option. Taylor *et al.* (2000) have referred to it as reader coaching and Pressley *et al.* (2001) called it scaffolding.

For reader coaching to be successful, Clark (2004) has listed three important criteria that must be met by parents and teachers/librarians who coach their children in reading:

- They must possess considerable explicit knowledge of phonics and English orthography. They need to understand the relationships between graphemes and phonemes and know how English words are put together.
- They must maintain a conscious awareness of their children’s instructional histories and anecdotal records of what they have taught and whom they have taught, and they have to refer to these records to plan their reading instructions.
- They must be aware of their children’s individual strengths and weaknesses. When coaching, they need to draw on their knowledge of phonics, orthography, instructional history, and their children’s abilities in a coordinated manner to provide tailored, moment-to-moment cues that help these children to identify and apply their knowledge of decoding strategies as they read for comprehension.

To sum up, reader coaching “is a powerful remedial technique that supports readers as they problem solve during meaningful reading experiences and develop reading independence” (Clark, 2004, p.448).

Reading Facilitation Role 3: Reader Empowerment

Reading behavior: Can read and do read

Reading equation:

$R = T(D + C) + M$ where all the elements are positive and high-functioning

To empower is to give someone more control or right over his/her own life or situation. In *reader empowerment*, the readers are given the control and rights over their reading activities. By this, I mean readers are given autonomy to select the books of their choice, to read at their respective paces, to engage in various reading-related activities (e.g., exploring a new theme, brain-storming over a topic, and doing a mini-project on reading) and the list can be endless.

Reader empowerment can be divided into three types: reader enrichment, reader enhancement, and reader enchantment. There is a distinction between the first two though they seem to mean almost the same. *To enrich* is like giving nourishment. Reader enrichment aims to improve the quality of a reader's decoding and comprehension skills as well as in the content area. Phonics, for example, will be a good reader enrichment program to help struggling readers to read better once they are aware of the letter sounds and taught phonological rules. On the other hand, *to enhance*, I see it as adding flavor to make reading look or taste better. Reader enhancement caters more to those independent readers who are already doing fine and they need to be challenged constantly to maximize their reading potential. Speed reading and thinking skills programs are good examples for such readers, but not everyone will benefit from it. Finally, *reader enchantment* has to do with one's state of being captivated by the magic of reading. The reader does not enchant what he/she reads, but rather becomes enchanted by what he/she reads. This is the highest of the three types of reader empowerment. *To be enchanted* is different from to enrich and to enhance. *To enrich* and *to enhance* are two explicit processes to stimulate a reader, but *to be enchanted* is an endogenous or implicit process whose stimulation comes from within the reader. It involves an evocation of the reader's thoughts and feelings that lead him/her into that meta-world of reading where he/she can take part in any adventure, journey or exploration. It makes the reader want to go on, read more and not to stop reading. In this case, the reader has gone beyond the level of automaticity in reading or self-monitoring of what he/she reads. He/She is now a part of that story and has become either a spectator or a participant in the story.

Application of $R = T(D + C) + M$, Reader Types and Reading Facilitation Roles

Understanding what the reading process involves allows us to understand how different reader types cope with it. This, in turn, enables us to plan a proper balanced reading program catering to the diversified needs of different readers through reading facilitation that involves reader counseling for reluctant readers, reader coaching for disabled readers, and reader empowerment for independent readers. The ultimate aim is to maximize the potential of every reader.

It is harder to urge older children, especially those who are already in the upper primary level, to pick up a book to read if they have never been encouraged or motivated to read when they were in the lower levels. They are the type 2 readers or reluctant readers.

Reading should begin at infancy phase. Parents play the most important role during this phase. Reading a book to a child sends an important message to him/her that reading is an essential part of one's life and later, a part of one's

life-long learning process. Hence, reading habits including phonological awareness should be developed at pre-school level. Once these pre-school children move up to the lower primary level (i.e., Primary 1 and 2), they should be at the emergent or early literacy level. They should have developed book or print awareness by this time and are expected to be reading books of their choices. Reader enrichment should be the focus at this level.

It is important to note that our children's reading habits should not be restricted only to academic reading (i.e., reading only the textbooks and doing workbooks and/or assessment books), but should also extend to recreational reading (i.e., reading beyond the academic demands/requirements). When they are in the middle primary level (i.e., Primary 3 and 4), their reading interests and tastes should be widened to include different literary genres. Reader enhancement and to some extent, reader enchantment should become our main focus at this level now. By the time they are in the upper primary, reading should become a part of their life-long learning habit and what they have learnt in reading now empowers them to progress further in their search for higher knowledge and skills.

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